

End-to-End Performance Comparison in Real-World Applications

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Abstract: This study presents an end-to-end performance comparison between two distinct hardware architectures: an Intel-based MacBook Pro equipped with DDR4 memory and an Apple M3 MacBook Pro featuring unified memory. The Intel system utilizes a 2.4 GHz 8-core Intel Core i9 processor (boostable to 5.0 GHz) with a 16 MB shared L3 cache, while the Apple M3 Max integrates a 16-core CPU and a 40-core GPU with a 400 GBps unified-memory bandwidth. In both environments, we measured and compared the inter-module latency across a complete video-processing pipeline, from video input to video output. The results highlight the architectural differences between discrete memory systems and unified memory architectures, particularly in how memory bandwidth, cache sharing, and data-transfer mechanisms affect real-time video processing performance. This evaluation provides practical insight into the impact of memory architecture and CPU-GPU integration on the end-to-end latency of real-world multimedia applications.

Fig. 1: Environment

Keywords: Edge Inference

1. 360p(640x360) 30 FPS

Table 1: 360p (640 × 360) 30 FPS

no	block	delay (ms)	note
0	Photon	0	
1	photon to RAM : HW encode	90-100	Intel CPU
2	Browser Engine WebGL Effect	30-40	video-tag → canvas-tag binding
3	VP8 encode + WebRTC media::send	1	< 1 ms
4	WebRTC media::recv + VP8 decode + Draw to UI object	1	App (libdatachannel) < 1 ms
4*	WebRTC media::recv + VP8 decode + Draw to UI object	1	Browser / Chrome (libwebrtc) < 1 ms

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2. Decoding

The following listing illustrates a representative hardware-accelerated (HWA) VP8 decoding pipeline, including bitstream ingestion, frame submission to the hardware decoder, and zero-copy transfer of decoded frames to the downstream compositor.

Listing 1: decode.cc

```
int decode(
    DECODE_INST pinst,
    const void* src,
    const unsigned src_len
)
{
    std::lock_guard<std::mutex> LOCK(cudaContextMutex);
    instance_ptr inst = (instance_ptr)(pinst);
    unsigned char* frame = (unsigned char*)src;
    unsigned frame_len = src_len;
    int frames = inst->decoder->Decode(
        frame,
        frame_len
    );
    for (int n = 0; n < frames; n++) {
        cudaError_t err;
        NppStatus nppstat;
        int rgbStepBytes;
        //
        auto pFrame = inst->decoder->GetFrame();
        auto width = inst->decoder->GetDecodeWidth();
        auto height = inst->decoder->GetHeight();
        auto fsize = inst->decoder->GetFrameSize();
        auto luma = inst->decoder->GetLumaPlaneSize();
        auto chroma = inst->decoder->GetChromaPlaneSize();
        auto dpBGRFrame = nppiMalloc_8u_C3(width, height, &rgbStepBytes);
        auto dpYCbCr420frame = nppiMalloc_8u_C3(width, height, &rgbStepBytes);

        Npp8u *planesAddress[2] = {
            pFrame,
            pFrame + luma
        };
        nppstat = nppiNV12ToRGB_8u_P2C3R(
            planesAddress,
            width,
            dpBGRFrame,
            width*3,
            { width, height }
        );
        if (nppstat != NPP_SUCCESS) {
            PANIC("failed. nppiNV12ToBGR_8u_P2C3R");
        }
        cudaMemcpy(
            inst->rgbBuffer,
            dpBGRFrame,
            3*inst->width*inst->height,
            cudaMemcpyDeviceToHost
        );
        nppiFree(dpBGRFrame);
        nppiFree(dpYCbCr420frame);
        if (inst->callback) {
            inst->callback(
                inst,
                (const char*)inst->rgbBuffer,
                inst->passthrough?fsize:3*inst->width*inst->height,
                inst->user
            );
        }
    }
    return(0);
}
```

3. Decoding Pipeline Latency Analysis results

We profiled the end-to-end VP8 decoding pipeline at three resolutions—360p (640×360), 720p (1280×720), and 1080p (1920×1080)—at 30 FPS, and separately compared CPU vs. GPU execution on two platforms (Apple M3 Max and Intel MacBook Pro). Across all experiments, the pipeline stages included: bitstream ingestion, VP8 decode, colorspace conversion, and handoff to the compositor/renderer.

3.1 Resolution-dependent bottlenecks

3.1.1 360p (640×360 @ 30 FPS).

The dominant source of latency was I420 \rightarrow ARGB colorspace conversion. At this resolution, decode itself is relatively light; memory traffic and per-pixel format conversion overhead overshadow codec runtime.

Fig. 2: Decoding pipeline, 360p (640×360) @ 30 FPS.

3.1.2 720p (1280×720 @ 30 FPS).

The primary bottleneck shifted to VP8 decode. Colorspace conversion remained non-trivial but no longer dominated the pipeline.

Fig. 3: Decoding pipeline, 720p (1280×720) @ 30 FPS.

3.1.3 1080p (1920×1080 @ 30 FPS).

VP8 decode remained the single largest contributor to frame latency. The growth in macroblock count and motion-comp effort scales codec cost faster than colorspace conversion at this resolution.

Fig. 4: Decoding pipeline, 1080p (1920×1080) @ 30 FPS.

Design implication. At lower resolutions, prioritize zero-copy surfaces and format alignment (e.g., keeping NV12/I420 through the compositor) to avoid ARGB conversion. At higher resolutions, focus on hardware decode paths, low-latency/no-reorder modes, and parallelizing bitstream submission.

3.2 CPU vs. GPU execution (platform comparison)

3.2.1 Apple M3 Max (Unified Memory).

GPU-accelerated decode and colorspace operations benefited from unified memory (high bandwidth, no explicit copies), reducing queuing and map/unmap overhead. This improved frame-to-frame consistency and lowered tail latency compared to CPU-bound paths.

Fig. 5: CPU vs. GPU on Apple M3 Max.

3.2.2 Intel Mac (DDR4 + discrete cache hierarchy).

CPU-bound decode paths incurred higher memory traffic and cache pressure during colorspace conversion and post-decode processing. Without unified memory, avoiding extra copies and ensuring cache-friendly scan order are critical for stability at 30 FPS in higher resolutions.

Fig. 6: CPU vs. GPU on Intel Mac.

Design implication. Prefer GPU/HWA decode with zero-copy handoff to the compositor/encoder where available. On non-unified-memory systems, minimize format churn and avoid CPU access to GPU surfaces.

4. Conclusion

This evaluation demonstrated that Unified Memory architecture and increased memory bus bandwidth have a substantial impact on VP8 decoding performance, yielding approximately a $2 \times$ improvement compared to traditional DDR4-based systems.

Because pixel setting and transfer operations in the decoding pipeline are dominated by memcpy-like memory transactions, the advantages of the Unified Memory structure were especially pronounced. The Apple M3 platform exhibited more than a $10 \times$ speed increase over the Intel Mac in these operations, primarily due to reduced data-copy overhead and higher memory throughput.

In the I420 \rightarrow ARGB color conversion stage, the M3 again outperformed the Intel system, achieving a $5 \times$ reduction in processing time. These results highlight the critical role of memory architecture and interconnect bandwidth in achieving real-time performance for video decoding and color-space conversion workloads in modern heterogeneous computing environments.